

ELIJAH LIEBSKIND

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SKILLS

Python

(Pandas, Statsmodels, BeautifulSoup, Scikit-Learn, PyTorch, BitsAndBytes, Numpy)

HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Git

Statistics

Descriptive, explanatory, and predictive statistics; linear and logistic regression; machine learning

Data

Scraping, data manipulation, visualization, annotation, and data generation using LLMs

Scientific approach

Scientific literature review, problem formulation, prediction, hypothesis testing, scientific communication

Langues

- French
- English

INTERESTS

- **Drawing** (caricatures and portraits)
- **Writing** (short stories and novels)
- **Theatre** (member of the RIDAU theatre association at Université PSL–Dauphine, 2023–2026)
- **Chess** (1800 Elo on Chess.com)

ACADEMIC BACKGROUND

Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (PSL) - Lycée Louis-Le-Grand – CPES Sciences des données, Arts et Cultures (2023 – 2026)

- **Mathematics:** Analysis – Algebra – Mathematics for Machine Learning
- **Computer Science:** Algorithms, Data Science, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Programming
- **One-week intensive course (PSL Week)** « Explainable Artificial Intelligence » PSL
- Sociology of Technology – Mines ParisTech

Baccalaureate (2023) : Distinction (15.42) Specializations: Mathematics, Physics–Chemistry, Visual Arts, Advanced Mathematics option

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Research Internship – École Normale Supérieure (2024–2025) : 350 hours – Supervised by Frédérique Mélanie–Becquet and Laure Sarda (CNRS)

- Implemented a computational program to identify character movements in novels
- Natural Language Processing & Python programming: Applied NLP methods to literary texts and Developed a program to extract triplets: Character + Motion Verb + Location

ACADEMIC PROJECTS

- **Research project:** construction of a model predicting the time spent playing a move in chess (publication of an online report and a GitHub repository to ensure project reproducibility) (2025)
- **Creation of a website** describing my academic background and research project, deployed on Render (2025)
- **Construction of a dataset** on contemporary watch sales, publication of the dataset on Harvard Dataverse and **writing of a research report** including quantitative and qualitative analyses of the selected segment (2025)

ARTISTIC PROJECTS

Theatre performance in English as part of the course Experimental Theatre Workshop at **New York University (Paris)** (2025)

Actor in the plays *Un Air de Famille* by Agnès Jaoui and Jean–Pierre Bacri (2023) and *Le Porteur d'Histoire* by Alexis Michalik (2024) – RIDAU Association – Université PSL–Dauphine

Stage direction: *Rhinocéros* by Eugène Ionesco and recipient of the Université PSL–Dauphine Culture Award (2025)

Writing of a short story as part of the **Solaar Punk PSL competition** (January 2026)